

Impact of poor iron status and its treatment on metabolomics profiles: a rapid review of human trials

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Abstract

Iron deficiency (ID) and anaemia (IDA) are global health concerns, particularly for women, who carry the greatest risk and burden. Although the clinical consequences of low iron are well documented, its broader impact on human metabolism is less clearly defined. Further, whilst the gut microbiome and the metabolites it produces impact host health, including nutrient status, the metabolic pathways linking iron status with systemic and gut microbial metabolites are poorly characterized. Identifying metabolite signatures of ID or iron overload may provide mechanistic insight into disease onset, progression, and response to intervention. Here we performed a rapid review of the literature using systematic methods to identify human studies reporting associations between iron status and metabolite profiles. PubMed and Google Scholar were searched using predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Titles and abstracts ($n = 72$) were screened, followed by full-text review of 30 articles. Seven studies met final eligibility and were included for data extraction and synthesis. Populations in captured studies included adults, pregnant people, and women of reproductive age, and included individuals with metabolic syndrome, colorectal cancer, or chronic renal failure. Despite heterogeneity in study designs and populations, several consistent metabolite classes were associated with iron status. Lower iron status was associated with diminished acyl-carnitines, glycerophosphocholines, phosphatidylcholines, porphyrins/heme, collagen-related metabolites, steroids, and microbial phenolic derivatives. By contrast, eicosanoids, proline, and lysophospholipids were generally enriched with lower iron status. Sex-specific associations were noted, with phenolic compounds and porphyrins more prominent in females with lower iron status and tryptophan/indoles in males with lower iron status. This rapid review highlights reproducible metabolic signatures associated with iron status across diverse human populations. These findings provide a foundation for targeted metabolite measurement in future trials and suggest potential biomarkers for monitoring iron-related health outcomes.

Keywords: Iron deficiency, iron deficiency anaemia, metabolomics, metabolites, gut microbiome, rapid review

Background

Iron deficiency (ID) and iron deficiency anaemia (IDA) remain among the most common nutritional deficiencies worldwide, with well-established effects on development and health¹, particularly for women who carry the greatest risk and burden of these conditions². Although the clinical consequences of low iron are well documented, its broader impact on human metabolism is less clearly defined¹. Metabolomics offers an effective approach to capture system-wide changes in small molecules that accompany poor iron status, possibly identifying biomarkers that reflect disease onset, progression, and treatment response¹. The gut microbiome, and the metabolites it produces, also impact host health, including nutrient status³ and drug response^{4,5} and gut microbial metabolites have been shown to be important for systemic iron homeostasis⁶. The relationship between gut microorganisms and micronutrients is bidirectional, where commensal microorganisms can regulate the levels of micronutrients both by intervening in biosynthetic processes and by modulating their absorption³. For example, gut microbiota can influence the bioavailability of minerals and vitamins through mechanisms such as the production of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), which lower gastrointestinal pH and facilitate mineral solubilization³. Research has demonstrated that gut microbiota explain up to 46% of the variance in individual plasma metabolites, with over 546,000 documented associations between specific gut metagenomic species and plasma metabolites⁴. These microbiome-metabolite

interactions have significant implications for host health, including effects on cardiovascular disease risk, metabolic disorders such as obesity and type 2 diabetes, and various chronic diseases including osteoporosis and cancer^{3,4}. Yet it remains unclear which metabolites, including of microbial origin, may reveal clues about iron status and ID pathogenesis. To explore the links between iron status and metabolite levels, we conducted a rapid review of human studies examining metabolomic profiles in the context of poor iron status, including ID/IDA. Our objectives were to: 1. summarize current evidence on whether and how metabolites change with poor iron status and its treatment; 2. highlight consistencies and exceptions to these relationships across studies and; 3. identify sex differences in relationships between iron status and metabolite profiles.

Methods

We report our process and findings guided by the National Collaborating Centre for Methods and Tools⁷ and the PRISMA reporting guidelines⁸.

Information sources and search terms

A literature search was conducted in PubMed and Google Scholar to identify studies examining gut microbial and circulating metabolites in relation to iron status or ID/IDA. The initial search was completed on August 19, 2024, with no lower date restriction applied, and captured 6

papers. A follow-up search was conducted from August 1, 2024 to August 7, 2025 to identify any new publications, which yielded one additional study. The PubMed search strategy combined MeSH terms and free-text keywords. The exposure terms included iron AND status AND/OR iron AND deficiency. Outcome terms included iron AND/OR ferritin AND/OR haemoglobin AND gut microbiome AND metabolite* OR metabolom*. Population terms were limited to human subjects. The full PubMed search string was: (iron AND status AND/OR iron AND deficiency) AND (iron AND/OR ferritin AND/OR haemoglobin AND gut microbiome AND metabolite* OR metabolom*) AND (human). Filters were applied to include randomized controlled trials, case series, controlled clinical trials, case-control studies, cross-sectional studies, and cohort/observational studies. The Google Scholar search was performed using the terms "gut microbiome metabolome and iron deficiency" to capture additional studies not indexed in PubMed.

Inclusion criteria

Studies were eligible for inclusion if they involved human participants and reported data on gut microbial metabolites or metabolic pathways in association with iron status indicators such as serum ferritin or haemoglobin. Studies that included interventions aimed at improving iron status with corresponding metabolite measurements were also considered. Only full-text articles published in English were included in the rapid review.

Article screening and data collection

A three-level screening process was performed by 2-3 individuals. At Level 1, 72 articles were captured and screened based on title and abstract for eligibility according to populations of interest, exposure criteria, outcomes of interest, and English language requirements. Following relevance assessment and deduplication, 30 articles remained for Level 2 screening. At Level 2, the full-text of these 30 articles were obtained and screened for eligibility based on exposure criteria related to iron status or deficiency measures, outcomes including gut microbial or circulating metabolites and metabolic classes/pathways, English language availability, study types of interest including randomized controlled trials, case series, controlled clinical trials, case-control studies, cross-sectional studies, and cohort/observational studies, full-text availability, and specific population considerations such as pregnancy status and type of dietary exposure or infection status. Studies were excluded if they were conducted in animal models, did not provide meaningful metabolite data (i.e. quantitative or qualitative information on specific metabolites, metabolite classes, or metabolic pathways measured in stool/faeces or circulation [serum/plasma]), or did not report metabolite data in relation to iron status (e.g., serum ferritin, haemoglobin/changes in iron status, including in response to interventions targeting ID/IDA). A final seven articles from both searches met inclusion criteria and were included in our evidence syntheses. At Level 3, data were extracted from these seven articles, including information relevant to the PI/ECO(T) framework, inclusion and exclusion criteria, data collection methods, and exposures and outcomes, as described below.

Data extraction, synthesis, and visualization

Data extraction was conducted in two phases. In Phase 1, information including PMID, study population, study design, metabolites measured, and key findings was collected from all studies meeting Level 2 screening criteria. In Phase 2, we extracted all reported metabolites from the articles included in Level 2 screening and noted their direction of change in relation to changing iron status. These metabolites/classes, whether measured in plasma or fecal samples, were organized into a comparative table alongside details of sample type, study population, specific

metabolite differences, and sex differences (Table 1). The primary exposure of interest was iron status, indicated by serum ferritin and haemoglobin levels or comparisons of ID/IDA vs. non-ID/IDA. The primary outcomes of interest were circulating and/or gut microbial metabolites measured pre- and post-intervention, between intervention and control groups, or between groups with ID/poor iron status versus groups with higher or normal iron status, without intervention. A comparative line plot was created to visualize how levels of metabolites within metabolite classes changed between low and higher iron status. Consistencies and inconsistencies in metabolite levels/enrichment trends across studies were noted. Sex differences and sex-specific effects for iron status-metabolite relationships were identified. We summarised details of included studies and their findings in a table.

Evidence Synthesis

Study design and demographics

Characteristics of the studies and a summary of the findings in relation to our outcomes are presented in Table 1. The studies in the seven articles captured were conducted across Europe (Germany N=820¹; Spain N=1030⁹; Austria N=163¹⁰) and Asia (China N=46¹¹; N=50¹²; N=558¹³; N=30¹⁴). In total, the studies encompassed 2697 participants. Forty-three percent of studies were conducted in Europe (3/7), with the remaining 57% of the studies being conducted in Asia (4/7). Seventy-one percent (5/7) studies were of mixed-sex^{1,9,10,12,13}, 29% (2/7) female-only^{11,14} and none were male-only. Populations ranged from healthy community-based cohorts to pregnant people, individuals with chronic renal failure (CRF), patients with colorectal cancer (CRC), women of reproductive age, and adults with metabolic syndrome (MetS). Study designs included observational cohort, case-control, and cross-sectional studies, as well as interventional approaches, including phlebotomy and a clinical trial of Buxue Yimu Pills. Sample types spanned plasma, serum, and fecal specimens, enabling assessment of both systemic and gut-derived metabolites in relation to iron status.

Distinct metabolite signatures differentiate low and higher iron status

Across the seven included studies, consistent metabolite patterns emerged that distinguish low from higher iron status (Table 1, Figure 1). Amino acid, lipid, and microbial-derived metabolites were the most frequently altered, with recurring signals in pathways related to energy metabolism, oxidative stress, and gut microbial activity. Several metabolite classes, including acyl-carnitines, glycerophosphocholines, p-cresol and related phenolic compounds, phosphatidylcholines, porphyrins/heme, collagen-related metabolites, and steroids, were enriched with higher iron status (Figure 1). By contrast, eicosanoids/arachidonic acid derivatives, proline, and lysophospholipids were consistently lower in higher iron states (Figure 1). Other classes such as purines/pyrimidines, sphingolipids, and tryptophan/indole derivatives showed inconsistent findings across studies (Figure 1). Mixed and inconsistent findings might be attributable to biospecimen type (fecal vs. serum/plasma) and clinical context. For lysophospholipids, LysoPC was inversely associated with ferritin levels in a population-based adult cohort (via positive association with transferrin levels), LysoPE decreased in anaemia and increased with treatment, whereas LysoPI increased with increasing ferritin levels in a community-dwelling cohort; additional lysophospholipid species were elevated in a cancer cohort with IDA. Purine/pyrimidine results differed by clinical context (e.g., uracil higher in pregnancy-associated ID/IDA but lower in anaemia of CRF), and tryptophan/indole metabolites were higher with increasing ferritin levels in a community-dwelling cohort, yet shifted in disease cohorts

(e.g., indole/kynurenic acid were elevated in CRF). Sphingolipid patterns were also context-dependent, where plasma sphingolipids tended to increase with increasing ferritin levels in community-based cohorts without major comorbidities, whereas fecal sphinganine/ceramide were elevated in cancer-associated IDA. Restricting the synthesis to cohorts without major comorbidities revealed three reproducible patterns. First, phosphatidylcholines (including plasmalogens) and acyl-carnitines were positively associated with serum ferritin levels and were decreased in anaemia. Second, microbial phenolics, specifically p-cresol and p-cresol sulfate, were reduced in low-iron states and increased with iron repletion. Third, proline was elevated with poorer iron status, whereas collagen-derived metabolite 4-hydroxyproline was decreased in anaemia and increased post-treatment (Table 1, Figure 1).

Limited data for sex differences or sex-specific relationships between iron status and metabolite levels

Sex-specific associations were evident in two of the articles. In the population-based adult cohort (plasma metabolomics cohort), the number

of statistically significant ferritin–metabolite associations was greater in women than men, where ferritin levels were positively associated with multiple lipid classes (phosphatidylcholines, sphingomyelins, acyl-carnitines, non-esterified fatty acids). In contrast in men, only a small subset of metabolites (e.g., LysoPC a C20:4, PC aa C38:4, arachidonate, 3-methyl-2-oxobutyrate) showed positive associations with ferritin levels. Further, this study reported inverse associations between metabolites and ferritin levels in women for selected phenolic conjugates (e.g., 3-hydroxyhippurate), and associations with transferrin levels, including positive associations with LysoPC C14:0 and tauroolithocholate-3-sulfate and inverse associations with betaine and PC aa C34:4. In the aging Imageomics cohort (community-dwelling), tryptophan/indole-pathway metabolites (indolyacryloylglycine, indolealdehyde, indoleacetaldehyde, indolelactic acid) were positively associated with ferritin levels predominantly in men, whereas phenylacetylglutamine was inversely associated with ferritin levels. Collectively, these studies suggest there are sex-specific iron-metabolite relationships in specific metabolite classes/pathways, however evidence remains limited.

Figure 1. Changes in metabolites/classes with iron status reported across seven studies. Red line = increasing levels/enrichment when moving from lower→higher iron status. Blue line = decreasing levels/diminishment when moving from lower→higher iron status. Dotted line = inconsistent findings across studies. Where tested: Pink (female) and blue (male) dots = sex-specific or sex-dominant associations. More phosphatidylcholine-iron status associations in women than men; indole derivatives increased with ferritin mainly in men. ♦ = Exceptions for changes in metabolite levels within the class trends: Acyl-carnitines (linoleyl-carnitine high with low iron); phenolic conjugates (phenylacetylglutamine, 3-hydroxyhippurate high with low iron); purines/pyrimidines (uracil high in pregnancy ID/IDA, low in CRF anaemia). Pop-out box: Direction of change in metabolite class from lower→higher iron status when examining data only from cohorts with ID/IDA and no other major comorbidities (Kaul 2018; Chen 2022; Guo 2022; Rosell-Díaz 2023).

Discussion

Here, we aimed to conduct a rapid review of evidence on the links between iron status and metabolite levels in humans, and identify how metabolite levels and enrichment of metabolic classes/pathways change with poor iron status and/or its treatment. We also aimed to identify whether relationships between iron status and metabolite profiles are sex-specific. Although the populations from the seven studies included in our synthesis were heterogeneous, we found a number of consistent changes between host iron status and circulating or gut microbial metabolites. When focusing on otherwise healthy populations, we identified phosphatidylcholine and acyl-carnitine levels were positively associated with iron status^{1,9}, suggesting these changes may be key metabolic responses to iron availability rather than disease-specific effects. Additionally, we found sex differences in iron-metabolite associations in two studies, with women showing a greater number of statistically significant associations between serum ferritin levels and lipid metabolites (phosphatidylcholines, sphingomyelins, acyl-carnitines, and non-esterified fatty acids), while men demonstrated positive associations between ferritin levels and tryptophan/indole catabolites that were not observed in women.

In circulating samples, the most consistently observed finding centred on phospholipid metabolism, with phosphatidylcholines (PCs) consistently decreased with poor iron status across multiple populations^{1,9,10}. Glycerophosphocholine (GPC) showed a parallel pattern, with levels lower with anaemia and increasing with treatment^{11,12}. Gut-derived metabolites also demonstrated consistent patterns with iron status, particularly microbial phenolics such as p-cresol and p-cresol sulfate, which were consistently lower with ID across both fecal¹³ and circulating^{9,10} samples. Mechanistically, iron participates directly in lipid metabolism through di-iron desaturases (e.g., stearoyl-CoA desaturase-1 [SCD1]) and related pathways that facilitate fatty-acid desaturation and phospholipid remodelling. Iron deficiency has been associated with impaired desaturation and altered phospholipid profiles, providing a potential mechanistic explanation for reduced circulating PCs in iron-depleted states^{15,16,117}. PCs constitute the predominant phospholipids of plasma lipoproteins and are essential for lipoprotein assembly¹⁷. Thus, diminished PC synthesis or remodelling would consequently reduce circulating PC concentrations¹⁷. The GPC patterns are consistent with altered PC turnover and choline recycling, given that GPC is derived from PC and undergoes hydrolysis by choline-specific glycerophosphodiesterases such as ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 6 (ENPP6)¹⁸. Regarding microbial phenolics, p-cresol represents the end-product of bacterial tyrosine fermentation via 4-hydroxyphenylacetate decarboxylase, which is a glycyl-radical enzyme requiring iron-sulfur (Fe-S)-cluster activation^{19,20}. Together with human data showing that intestinal iron availability influences microbial community composition and metabolic function, reduced iron status may diminish p-cresol-producing taxa^{19,20,21}. These mechanisms need to be fully explored in future studies.

Several metabolite classes showed inconsistent patterns with iron status. While lysophospholipids, sphingolipids, and tryptophan-indole metabolites varied in their directional associations with iron status, even within these inconsistent classes, specific metabolites showed reliable patterns. The mixed findings likely reflect differences in underlying disease states, ID severity, and population characteristics across studies.

Although we found we found sex-specific signals in two cohorts (more ferritin-lipid associations in women¹ and predominantly male ferritin-

tryptophan/indole associations⁹), there was a dearth of data on sex differences or sex-specific effects for iron-host/microbial metabolite relationships. This is despite that women carry the greatest burden and risk for ID/IDA⁴, as these conditions affect 1/3 of women globally²², 40% of women of reproductive age³, and 52% of pregnancies^{22,23}, and women experience inadequate diagnosis, prevention, and treatment². This bias in metabolomics research must be addressed to better understand ID/IDA pathogenesis and treatment response, and to develop targeted biomarkers and interventions for the population at most risk.

Strengths and Limitations

A strength of this rapid review is that it applied a systematic approach to capture evidence on whether and how metabolites change with poor iron status and its treatment. We also aimed to identify sex differences or sex-specific relationships, data that are lacking across metabolomics literature. Limitations include the relatively small number of available studies, incomplete methodological reporting in some articles, and the possibility that the rapid nature of the review may have missed of some relevant literature. Our synthesis suggests that specific metabolite signatures, particularly reductions in phosphatidylcholines and acyl-carnitines, may serve as key markers of impaired iron status across diverse populations. These reproducible associations highlight the potential for developing metabolite-based indicators of iron status trajectory and/or response to treatment that extend beyond conventional biomarkers such as ferritin and haemoglobin, revealing additional information on mechanistic underpinnings of ID/IDA and host health. These findings also provide a foundation for targeted metabolite measurement in future studies that aim to monitor iron-related health outcomes.

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Table 1 Summary of study characteristics and findings

Study	Population & methods	Sample type	Metabolites elevated in ID/IDA (vs. control/normal iron)	Metabolites lower in ID/IDA (vs. control/normal iron)	Sex differences or sex-specific findings
Kaul (2018)	Population-based sample (cross-sectional), Germany; N=820; 409M/411F; age (median [IQR] men 50 [40-61] y, women 54 [44-62] y)	Plasma	Inverse association with ferritin: 1-oleoylglycerophosphoinositol, 3-hydroxyhippurate; Positive association with transferrin: LysoPC C14:0, tauroolithocholate 3-sulfate, betaine, PC aa C34:4	Positive association with ferritin: Hexanoylcarnitine, arachidonate (20:4n6), biliverdin, 3-methyl-2-oxobutyrate, 4-methyl-2-oxopentanoate, leucine, valine, PC ae C36:4, PC ae C40:2, PC aa C38:4, SM (OH) C22:1, SM C24:1, SM C16:1, γ -glutamylleucine, piperine, 7 α -hydroxy-3-oxo-4-cholestenoate, lactate, phosphate, threonine	Women: More metabolite associations than men. Men: Ferritin positively associated with LysoPC a C20:4, PC aa C38:4, arachidonate, 3-methyl-2-oxobutyrate; transferrin positively associated with creatine
Chen (2022)	Pregnant women (N=30), China; ID without anaemia (n=10), IDA (n=10), healthy pregnant controls with normal iron status (n=10)	Fecal	Catechol, xanthine, uracil, L-proline, ornithine, thiamine aldehyde, L-2,4-diaminobutyric acid, 1-aminocyclopropanecarboxylic acid, L-threonine, pyrroline hydroxycarboxylic acid	Dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA), cholesterol, catecholate (siderophore), methyl β -D-galactoside, gentisic acid, deoxyinosine, homovanillic acid (HVA)	N/A (all female participants)
Stechemesser (2017) - Cross-sectional	Cross-sectional, Austria; N = 163; M/F = 81/82; Ages (mean \pm SD): controls 54.7 \pm 7.9 y, MetS-Fe 56.4 \pm 6.4 y, MetS+Fe 58.3 \pm 9.2 y. Groups: healthy controls n=53, MetS-Fe n=54, MetS+Fe n=56	Plasma	Iron overload associations: Sarcosine, citrulline, methionine sulfoxide, PC 40:2, PC 40:3, PC 40:4, PC 42:1, PC 42:6	-	N/A
Stechemesser (2017) - Phlebotomy	Pre-post phlebotomy intervention, Austria;	Plasma	Decreased after iron removal: PC 36:0, PC 38:0, PC 38:1, PC 40:2, PC	Increased after iron removal: Methionine	N/A

	N = 30; M/F = 28/2; Age (mean ± SD): 56.1 ± 7.4 y; sampling before first and 10–14 days after final phlebotomy		40:3, PC 42:0, PC 42:1, PC 42:4, PC_E36:1, PC_E38:1, PC_E38:2, PC_E38:3, PC_E40:1, PC_E40:2, PC_E40:3, PC_E40:4, PC_E40:5, PC_E42:1, PC_E44:3, glutamate		
Zhang (2024) - CRC with IDA	Adults with colorectal cancer; IDA CRC (n=69), non-anaemic CRC patients (n=245), healthy controls free from GI tumours and anaemia (n=244)	Fecal	Higher in IDA vs Controls: Protoporphyrin IX, prostaglandin H ₂ , lucidenic acid D1, perfluorooctanesulfonic acid, harderoporphyrinogen, DG (18:1/18:2), D-erythro-sphinganine, Asp-Pro dipeptide, N- cyclohexanecarbonyltetradecylamine, 3-(4-fluorobenzoyl) propionic acid, 1,2-dilinoleoylglycerol, isoamyl p- anisate, 3-pyridinecarboxylic acid, N- methyl-D-glucamine, SQDG(13:1/13:1), trimethylpropylpyrazine, CerNS, N- oleoyl phenylalanine, Ala-His	Lower in IDA vs Controls: Trimethoxyflavanone, secoisolariciresinol, D- galacturonic acid, 4- methylumbelliferyl heptanoate, trans-ferulic acid, quinic acid, austroinulin, 4- hydroxybenzoic acid, soyasaponin Bb, 5,7- dihydroxy-3',4',5'- trimethoxyflavanone, valeric acid, 2- indolecarboxylic acid; Both CRC groups vs Controls: Valeric acid (SCFA)	N/A
Zhang (2024) - IDA vs Non-anaemic CRC	Adults with colorectal cancer; IDA CRC (n=62) vs non- anaemic CRC patients (n=215), healthy controls (n=244)	Fecal	Higher in IDA vs Non-anaemic: LysoPE 17:2, lucidenic acid D1	Lower in IDA vs Non- anaemic: 2-hydroxy-4,7- dimethoxy-2H-1,4- benzoxazin-3-one, austroinulin	N/A
Rosell-Díaz (2023)	Aging Imageomics cohort (N=1030), Spain; 557M/473F, mean age 67.1 ± 7.4 y	Plasma	Positive association with ferritin: indolylacryloylglycine, indolealdehyde, indoleacetaldehyde, indole lactic acid, cresol (p-cresol), LysoPI (20:5), PC(P-36:3), eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA), sphingomyelin SM(d36:2), hydroxybutyric acid	Negative association with ferritin: phenylacetylglutamine, ureidobutyric acid (ureidoisobutyric acid), proline, linoleyl carnitine, phosphatidylinositol phosphate (PIP 36:4)	Results were more consistent with the overall cohort findings. Women: Different pattern - ferritin negatively associated with proline, linoleyl carnitine, and phosphatidylinositol phosphate (PIP (36:4)), while positively associated with EPA, sphingomyelin(d36:2),

					and hydroxybutyric acid. Results were less consistent with men and overall cohort.
Ying-ying (2023)	Single-arm pre–post clinical trial, China; N=46, women of reproductive age (24-52 y, median 41 y)	Serum	Metabolites lower in anaemia (increased after treatment): chenodeoxycholic/ursodeoxycholic acid, homoveratric acid, 2,3-/3,4-dihydroxybenzoate, p-cresol sulfate, 4-hydroxy-L-proline, trans-4-hydroxyproline, hippurate, 2,6-dimethylheptanoyl carnitine, trimethylamine N-oxide (TMAO), indoxyl sulfate, decanoyl-, dodecanoyl-/lauroyl-carnitine, 4,8-dimethylnonanoyl carnitine, 4-hydroxyindole, glycerylphosphorylethanolamine, 3-indoleacetic acid, L-octanoylcarnitine, phosphorylcholine, glycerophosphocholine, LPE (18:2)-H, LysoPE (18:1)	Metabolite higher in anaemia (lower after treatment): 4-pyridoxic acid	N/A
Wang (2025)	Case-control study (N=50), China; M/F=23/27; CRF-anaemia n=30 vs healthy controls with normal renal function n=20, matched for sex and age; ages (mean ± SD): HC 62.6 ± 8.3 y, CRF-anaemia 61.1 ± 10.3 y	Fecal & serum	Fecal – higher in anaemia: 12-keto-tetrahydro-leukotriene B ₄ (12-KETE-LTB ₄). Serum – higher in anaemia: creatinine, gluconic acid, 4-hydroxyphenylacetaldehyde, D-glucuronic acid, indole, kynurenic acid, 17 α ,21-dihydroxypregnenolone, choline sulfate, levonorgestrel, 9-cis-retinoic acid, indole-3-carboxylic acid, dulcin	Fecal – lower in anaemia: uracil, L-aspartic acid, gulonic acid. Serum – lower in anaemia: L-valine, indolelactic acid, glycerophosphocholine.	N/A

Study characteristics are presented according to population, sample type, study design, and main findings. M = male; F = female; y = years of age; ID = iron deficiency, IDA = iron deficiency anaemia; MetS = metabolic syndrome; MetS+Fe = metabolic syndrome with iron overload; MetS-Fe = metabolic syndrome without iron overload; CRC = colorectal cancer; CRF = chronic renal failure.

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